

Complexes of 3-Amino(pyrid-2-yl)thiourea with Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II)

R. K. PATEL* and R. N. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008

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The complexes of 3-amino(pyrid-2-yl)thiourea having the stoichiometry ML_2X_n , where $M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$; $L =$ ligand; $X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-$ and ClO_4^- , have been prepared and characterised by magnetic, conductance, uv and ir spectral studies. The ir spectra reveals bidentate nature of the ligand and the electronic spectra suggest the octahedral geometry. All the complexes are paramagnetic in nature.

TRANSITION metal complexes using sulphur donor ligands are quite important as insecticide and fungicide¹ and are used in analytical chemistry². They are also finding use in vulcanisation of rubber, in the flotation process for concentration of ore³. It was therefore thought worthwhile to prepare some complexes using the title ligand with Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} .

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand was prepared from *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-3-amino(pyrid-2-yl)thiocarbamide which was prepared earlier by standard procedure⁴. *N*-Benzoyl-*N'*-3-amino(pyrid-2-yl)thiocarbamide (25 g) was boiled with sodium hydroxide solution (15%) for 30 min

and then filtered in hot. The filtrate on acidification with concentrated HCl yields a grey precipitate. This was made alkaline with concentrated ammonium hydroxide. On standing overnight, a viscous liquid of greenish grey colour was obtained which was separated on a separating funnel and washed several times in water. The compound was kept 24 h in vacuum and the resulting greenish grey product was dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of complexes: A solution of the ligand (0.2 mol) in acetone was added dropwise to a hot solution of the metal salt MX_2 (where $M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II} ; $X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-, ClO_4^-$) (0.1 mol) in ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h and then 50% solvent was allowed to

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			
			M	N	S	Cl/Br
APTU	Greenish grey	–				
$Cu(APTU)_2Cl_2$	Steel grey	1.76	20.5 (20.9)	18.0 (18.5)	10.2 (10.6)	23.0 (23.5)
$Cu(APTU)_2Br_2$	Grey	1.79	15.9 (16.2)	13.9 (14.3)	7.9 (8.2)	40.5 (40.9)
$Cu(APTU)_2(NO_3)_2$	Green	1.71	17.5 (17.8)	23.3 (23.6)	8.7 (9.0)	–
$Cu(APTU)_2(ClO_4)_2$	Greenish yellow	1.76	14.7 (15.1)	13.0 (13.3)	7.1 (7.6)	16.4 (16.9)
$Co(APTU)_2Cl_2$	Bluish white	4.83	19.4 (19.8)	18.4 (18.8)	10.4 (10.7)	23.4 (23.8)
$Co(APTU)_2Br_2$	Faint blue	4.92	14.9 (15.2)	14.1 (14.5)	8.0 (8.3)	40.9 (41.4)
$Co(APTU)_2(NO_3)_2$	Olive green	4.82	16.3 (16.8)	23.6 (23.9)	9.0 (9.1)	–
$Co(APTU)_2(ClO_4)_2$	Dark yellow	4.80	13.7 (13.8)	13.2 (13.1)	7.3 (7.5)	16.3 (16.7)
$Ni(APTU)_2Cl_2$	Canary yellow	3.18	19.2 (19.7)	18.3 (18.8)	10.4 (10.7)	23.5 (23.8)
$Ni(APTU)_2(Br)_2$	Brown	3.02	14.7 (15.1)	14.1 (14.5)	8.1 (8.3)	41.0 (41.4)
$Ni(APTU)_2(NO_3)_2$	Pale violet	3.04	16.3 (16.7)	23.7 (24.0)	8.7 (9.1)	–
$Ni(APTU)_2(ClO_4)_2$	Violet	3.16	13.4 (13.8)	13.0 (13.2)	7.0 (7.5)	16.3 (16.7)

evaporate. The resulting complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were found insoluble in water and common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF.

The elemental analysis were performed by standard methods⁵. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy method. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a Toshniwal CL-54 spectrophotometer. The conductance measurements were carried out in a Toshniwal CL-01-06 conductivity bridge using $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ DMF solutions. The colour, magnetic moment and analytical data of complexes are summarised in Table I.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis of the complexes correspond to the formula ML_2X_2 (where $M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II} ; $X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-$ and ClO_4^- ; $L = \text{ligand}$). Molar conductance values of the complexes were found to be less than $30 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ suggesting non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The monomeric structure of the complexes were suggested by molecular weight measurement (Rast's camphor method). The Cu^{II} complexes possess normal magnetic susceptibility value of 1.71–1.79 B.M. as expected for octahedral Cu^{II} . The Co^{II} complexes possess magnetic moment values of 4.8–4.92 B.M. expected for high-spin octahedral Co^{II} . The Ni^{II} complexes have the magnetic moment values of 3.02–3.18 B.M. which are in accordance with octahedral complexes.

The ir spectra of 3-amino(pyrid-2-yl)thiourea is quite complex, but attempts have been made to characterise certain important bands which show considerable structural significance of the ligand and its metal complexes. The structure of the ligand can be represented by three different tautomeric form as in (a), (b) and (c). The structure (a) contains thioketo group and the other two contain thiol group. However, the ir spectra provide ample evidence in favour of the existence of the ligand in thioketo form (a).

In the high frequency region, the ligand shows a broad ir band in the range $3400 - 3200 cm^{-1}$

(NH and NH_2) and a strong band at $\sim 3100 cm^{-1}$ (CH stretching of aromatic ring). Further, the nature and width of the former band into a number of small components suggest the presence of two different types of NH_2 group, one linked to pyridine ring and the other thiomide linkage. There is no ν_{S-H} band at $2600 - 2400 cm^{-1}$ which is an additional evidence for structure (a). The next group of bands observed in the spectra of the ligand are at $1600, 1570, 1480$ and $1430 cm^{-1}$. These band, in our opinion, arises due to NH_2 deformation, ν_{C-N} ⁶ of pyridyl- N^7 ν_{C-N} and ν_{C-S} vibrations respectively⁸. The other bands observed are at $1340, 1290, 1260$ and $1050 cm^{-1}$, which may be due to 1,2-disubstituted-pyridine ring. There are four weak bands in the region $915 - 780 cm^{-1}$ in the ligand, which may be due to out-of-plane CH bending of the disubstituted pyridine ring. Another band at $730 cm^{-1}$ is observed due to $\nu_{C=S}$ vibration.

In the metal complexes, the ir spectra show a relatively asymmetric broad band in the range $3400 - 3100 cm^{-1}$ being overlapped with CH stretching vibration of the aromatic ring. These spectral features suggest that one of the NH_2 groups has been coordinated to metal ion and other may be free, consequently leading to the lowering of the stretching frequency of the coordinated NH_2 group. In view of the favourable ring size, we suggest coordination of the NH_2 group adjacent to pyridine ring with the metal ion. The ν_{C-N} band at $1480 cm^{-1}$ is increased to higher frequency region by $30 - 40 cm^{-1}$. The ν_{C-S} band undergoes a shift by $40 - 50 cm^{-1}$ towards lower frequency region due to coordination with metal ions in the complexes. The bands at $915 - 780 cm^{-1}$ in the ligand shift in an irregular way in the metal complexes. The $\nu_{C=S}$ band at $730 cm^{-1}$ in the ligand undergoes a red-shift and appears at $\sim 695 cm^{-1}$ in the metal complexes, which suggests the coordination of the ligand to the metal ion through S atom⁹.

In the ir spectra of nitrate complexes, the bands of the coordinated N–O of the NO_3 are observed at $\sim 1470, 1260, 1020$ and $980 cm^{-1}$ respectively¹⁰. In the perchlorate complexes bands at $1260, 1130$ and $1000 cm^{-1}$ are observed¹¹. The bands appearing at $\sim 470 - 430$ and $420 - 340 cm^{-1}$ of the complexes, have been tentatively assigned to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-S} respectively^{12,13}. The ir spectral data and stoichiometry lead us to propose the following structure I

N–S–Ligand; $X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-$ and ClO_4^-

for the metal complexes. The structure find support from electronic spectra.

Electronic spectra: The Cu^{II} complexes show a broad band at $14\,300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon=48$) which can be assigned to the transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$. Besides, a band around $26\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon=158$) is observed which may be due to charge transfer band. It is reported that the Cu^{II} complexes in an octahedral environment show broad band around $12\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. But this is highly sensitive to Jahn-Teller distortion. The band in the present study indicates that the distortion brought about in the complex is due to Jahn-Teller effect¹⁴. The Co^{II} complexes exhibit two bands at $\sim 9\,100$ (170) and $18\,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (48) which may be assigned to the transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) \nu_3$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) \nu_3$ respectively, in an approximately octahedral field¹⁴. A charge transfer band is observed at $27\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes, three well-resolved bands observed at $9\,800$, $16\,400$ and $25\,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) \nu_1$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) \nu_3$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) \nu_3$ transitions respectively, under an octahedral environment around Ni^{II} ion¹⁵. The ϵ values could not be calculated as the saturated solutions are taken for the Ni^{II} complexes.

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